

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Research and Development Expenditures in Europe

In 2021 France and Germany totaled 50% of European expenditure in research and development

The Eurostat calculates the value of gross internal expenditure for research and development. This is the sum of the expenditure in research and development connected to resident companies, research institutes, university and government laboratories that are carried out on the national territory.

Ranking of European countries for the value of shopping in research and development in 2021. Germany is in the first place for the value of shopping in research and development in 2021 with an amount equal to 11,285 million euros, followed by France with 55,317.06 million Euro, and from Italy with 26,516.92 million euros. In the middle of the standings there are Ireland with an amount of 4,501.54 million euros, followed by Portugal with an amount of 4,501.54 million euros, followed by Greece with 2,635.23 million euros. Latvia with 232.20 million euros close the ranking, followed by Cyprus with 208.00 million euros and Malta with 94.99 million euros.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage change in research and development between 2012 and 2021. Cyprus is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the expenditure in research and development between 2012 and 2021 with an amount of 143, 78% equal to an amount of 122.68 million euros, followed by Poland with an amount of 140.62% or equal to an amount of 4,823.02 million euros, and Croatia with an amount of 119.73% even to an amount of 395.11 million euros. In the middle of the standings there are Latvia with an amount of 58.48% equal to a value of 333.13 million euros, followed by Slovakia with a value of 56.92% equal to an amount of 333.13 million euros e from the Netherlands with an amount of 54.37% equal to an amount of 6,803.38 million euros. Slovenia closes the ranking with an amount of 20.33% equal to an amount of 188.69 million euros, followed by France with a value of 18.91% equal to an amount of 8798.02 million euros and Finland with a value of 9.65% equal to an amount of 659.21 million euros.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented below. Specifically, the following Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Belgium, Austria, Denmark, Norway, Finland, Poland, Malta Cyprus, Latvia, Estonia, Bulgaria, Lithuania, Croatia, Ireland, Czech Republic, Luxembourg, Slovakia, Romania, Slovenia, Portugal, Hungary, Greece;
- Cluster 2: Germany, France.

From the point of view of the median, the following system of the Clusters or $C2 = 84083.5 > C1 = 3100.08$ is the following system. The analysis shows that France and Germany guide the ranking of the countries for the value of the shopping in research and development by marking a considerable difference with the rest of Europe.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Network Analysis with the use of Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is analyzed below using the Euclidean distance. Three complex network structures are identified. There is a network structure between the following countries or:

- Luxembourg has a connection with Slovakia for a value of 0.011 units and with Romania for a value of 0.021 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Luxembourg for a value equal to 0.011 units and with Romania for a value of 0.019 units;
- Romania has a connection with Luxembourg for a value of 0.021 units and with Slovakia for a value of 0.019 units.
- In addition, there is a complex network structure between the following countries or:
- Cyprus has a connection with Malta for a value of 0.0056 units, and with Latvia for a value of 0.0058 units;
- Malta has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.0056 and with Latvia for a value of 0.01 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Malta for a value of 0.01 units and with Cyprus with a value of 0.0058 units.

The following complex economic structure is also detected or:

- Lithuania has a connection with Croatia for a value of 0.0063 units, with Estonia for a value of 0.0079 units, with Bulgaria for a value of 0.0048;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.0048 units, with Estonia for a value of 0.01 units, with Croatia equal to 0.0077 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Bulgaria for a value of 0.01 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.0077 units, and with Croatia for a value of 0.011 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Bulgaria for a value of 0.0077, with Estonia for a value of 0.011 units, and with Lithuania for a value of 0.0063 units.

Conclusions. The average value of the expenditure for research and development in European countries considered went from an amount of 8,682.2 million euros in 2012 up to a value of 12,018.5 million euros or equal to a growth of an amount of 3,336.31 million of euros equal to an amount of 38.43%. However, there is a huge distinction between European countries in terms of investment in research and development. In fact, France, and Germany in 2021 totaled about 50% of the expenditure in research and development, followed by Italy with 7.88%, the Netherlands with 5.74% and Sweden with 5.35%. It therefore follows that most European countries has a negligible research and development of research. However, it is necessary to identify methodologies that can allow the growth of shopping in research and development as a preliminary element with respect to the growth of competitiveness in high-tech sectors.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516438>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Individuals with Risk Behaviors in the Consumption of Alcohol in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636364>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Years of Life Lost for Exposure to PM2.5 in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799937>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Perception of Good Health in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799948>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Healthy Life Expectancy in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799956>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Nitrate in Groundwater in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799995>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806877>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Use of Hazardous Pesticides in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806908>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Areas Cultivated with Organic Agriculture in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806941>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Public Expenditure for Research and Development in Agriculture in EU, USA, and Japan. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806965>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Material and Social Deprivation in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811428>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Workers at Risk of Poverty in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811442>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Turnover in the Service Sector in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811492>

Leogrando, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrando, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrando, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Leogrando, A., & Costantiello, A. (2021). Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrando, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Leogrando, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(10), 72-101.

Leogrando, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The determinants of human resources in European countries during the period 2010-2019. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(9), 145-171.

Leogrando, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrando, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. European Journal of Educational Management, 2(2), 85-110.

Appendix

Clusterizzazione. C2>C1.

■ C1

■ C2

